

Table S1: Notation summary

\underline{m}	complete spectral dataset consisting of N MS/MS spectra
\underline{m}_n	the n -th MS/MS spectrum of the spectra dataset (\underline{m})
K_n	number of m/z fragment peaks in the n -th MS/MS spectrum
m_{nk}	the k -th m/z fragment peak of the n -th MS/MS spectrum
\underline{c}_n	candidate list/set for the n -th MS/MS spectrum
C_n	size/length of candidate list/set \underline{c}_n
c_{nc}	c -th candidate of candidate list/set \underline{c}_n
f_{nck}	fragment-structure (of candidate c_{nc}) assigned to m/z fragment peak m_{nk}
$(\underline{m}_n, \underline{f}_{nc})$	peak fragment assignment of candidate c_{nc} to MS/MS spectrum \underline{m}_n
\perp	placeholder indicating a non-annotated annotated m/z fragment peak
\tilde{f}_k	fingerprint of fragment-structure f_k
\tilde{M}_{tr}	reduced m/z fragment peak domain (for training MS/MS spectra)
\tilde{F}_{tr}	reduced fingerprint domain (for training MS/MS spectra)
\mathcal{D}_{train}	list of single peak fragment assignments
\underline{m}_q	query MS/MS spectrum
m_{qk}	the k -th m/z fragment peak of the query MS/MS spectrum
f_{qck}	fragment-structure (of candidate c_{qc}) assigned to m/z fragment peak m_{qk}
K_q	number of m/z fragment peaks in the query MS/MS spectrum
C_q	candidate list/set of query MS/MS spectrum \underline{m}_1
\tilde{M}	reduced m/z fragment peak domain (for training MS/MS spectra + query MS/MS spectrum)
\tilde{F}	reduced fingerprint domain (for training MS/MS spectra + query MS/MS spectrum)
$\theta_{mf} \sim$	probability of fragment fingerprint \tilde{f} given m/z fragment peak m
θ_{mf}^{ML}	maximum likelihood estimator for $\theta_{mf} \sim$
$N_{mf} \sim$	absolute frequency of observing fragment fingerprint \tilde{f} and m/z fragment peak m
$N_{m\perp}$	absolute frequency of observing a non-annotated m/z fragment peak m
$\pi_{mf} \sim$	hyper parameter for prior distribution
α, β	pseudo counts for prior distribution
θ_{mf}^{ML}	mean posterior estimator for $\theta_{mf} \sim$
l_{nkh}	m/z fragment loss between m/z fragment peaks m_{nk} and m_{nh}
f_{nchk}	fragment-substructure of f_{nck} excluding f_{nch} assigned to l_{nkh}
\tilde{L}_{tr}	reduced m/z fragment loss domain (for training MS/MS spectra)
\tilde{F}_{tr}^L	reduced loss fingerprint domain (for training MS/MS spectra)
\mathcal{D}_{train}^L	list of single loss fragment assignments
\tilde{M}^L	reduced m/z fragment loss domain (for training MS/MS spectra + query MS/MS spectrum)
\tilde{F}^L	reduced loss fingerprint domain (for training MS/MS spectra + query MS/MS spectrum)
$\psi_{mf} \sim$	hyper parameter for prior distribution of fragment loss model
α^L, β^L	pseudo counts for prior distribution of fragment loss model
$\phi_{lf} \sim$	probability of loss fragment fingerprint \tilde{f} given m/z fragment peak m
ϕ_{lf}^{ML}	maximum likelihood estimator for $\psi_{lf} \sim$
$N_{lf}^L \sim$	absolute frequency of observing fragment loss fingerprint \tilde{f} and m/z fragment loss m
$S_{MetFrag}^c$	MetFrag score of a candidate c
S_{Peak}^c	statistical score evaluating fragment - m/z peak assignments of a candidate c
S_{Loss}^c	statistical score evaluating loss fragment - m/z loss assignments of a candidate c
$S_{RawPeak}^c$	non-normalized statistical score evaluating fragment - m/z peak assignments of a candidate c
$\omega_1, \omega_2, \omega_3$	single score weights
S_{Fin}^c	final/consensus score of a candidate c